

Not so Slow

Do Galactic Bars Slow Down?

UGC 12158, ESA/Hubble & NASA

Angus "Gus" Beane (CfA)

with Lars Hernquist (CfA), **Elena D'Onghia (UW-Madison)**, Federico Marinacci (Bologna), Charlie Conroy (CfA), Jia "Alex" Qi (UF), Laura V. Sales (UC-Riverside), Paul Torrey (UF), Mark Vogelsberger (MIT)

Galactic bars: driving and decoding galaxy evolution

Jul 4 🇺🇸, 2023

We expect barred galaxies to slow down

But most observed bars are FAST

Many Galaxies are Barred

slow

how fast the bar is rotating

fast

We expect barred galaxies to slow down

GALAKOS Model

THE ASTROPHYSICAL JOURNAL, 890:117 (14pp), 2020 February 20
© 2020. The American Astronomical Society. All rights reserved.

<https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab6bd6>

Trojans in the Solar Neighborhood

Elena D'Onghia^{1,3} and J. Alfonso L. Aguerri^{2,4}

¹ Department of Astronomy, University of Wisconsin, 475 North Charter Street, Madison, WI 53706, USA

² Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias, Calle Via Lactea, E-38205, La Laguna, Spain

Received 2019 July 17; revised 2019 December 7; accepted 2020 January 6; published 2020 February 19

Circular Velocity

Observations
from Sofie+09

t=0.00 Myr

edge on

face on

GALAKOS Model

- Reasonable match to Milky Way observations
 - Pattern speed of the bar (40 km/s/kpc)
 - Length of the bar (~4.5 kpc)
 - Circular velocity curve consistent with Milky Way's

30 kpc x 30 kpc

GALAKOS Model

Why does the bar slow down?

Why does the bar slow down?

Only halo material resonant with the bar will form the wake.

$$F_{\text{dyn}} \sim \frac{M^2 \rho}{v_{\text{rel}}^2}$$

Why does the bar slow down?

**bar excites wake at
resonance**

Why does the bar slow down?

bar excites wake at resonance

bar slows down, changing location of resonance

Why does the bar slow down?

bar excites wake at resonance

bar slows down, changing location of resonance

bar excites wake at new location of resonance

Why does the bar slow down?

Why does the bar slow down?

the wake must lag the bar to slow it down

SMUGGLE Model

- Built upon the moving-mesh code **AREPO**
- Includes energy, momentum, mass, and metallicity

- **SNe feedback** (radiation pressure from OB stars, stellar winds from OB/AGB, photoionization)
- **SNe feedback** (Ia and II)

SMUGGLE Model

GALAKOS Model

GALAKOS Model

Why doesn't the bar slow down?

torque on bar

Why doesn't the bar slow down?

the gas applies a constant positive torque to the bar

the halo torque is neutralized?

(this is the point of the talk)

Why doesn't the bar slow down?

bar excites wake at resonance

bar slows down, changing location of resonance

bar excites wake at new location of resonance

Why doesn't the bar slow down?

bar excites wake at resonance

bar slows down, changing location of resonance

bar excites wake at new location of resonance

Why doesn't the bar slow down?

bar excites wake at resonance

bar slows down, changing location of resonance

Why doesn't the bar slow down?

bar excites wake at resonance

bar slows down, changing location of resonance

bar (and wake) speed up due to gas, but no new wake can form

Why doesn't the bar slow down?

the wake must lag the bar to slow it down

Why doesn't the bar slow down?

saturation of trapping

Why doesn't the bar slow down?

the gas applies a constant torque to the bar

the halo torque is neutralized

This effect is seen in other simulations

Mon. Not. R. Astron. Soc. **000**, 1–6 (2013) Printed 26 February 2018 (MN \LaTeX style file v2.2)

Bar slowdown and the distribution of dark matter in barred galaxies

E. Athanassoula*
Aix Marseille Université, CNRS, LAM (Laboratoire d'Astrophysique de Marseille), UMR 7326, 13388, Marseille, France

Accepted 2013 November 13. Received 2013 November 11; in original form 2013 October 10

c 2013

This effect is seen in other simulations

Astronomy & Astrophysics manuscript no. Fragkoudi_etal_2021
May 26, 2021

©ESO 2021

Revisiting the tension between fast bars & the Λ CDM paradigm

F. Fragkoudi^{1,2*}, R. J. J. Grand², R. Pakmor², V. Springel², S. D. M. White², F. Marinacci³, F. A. Gomez^{4,5}, and J. F. Navarro⁶

¹ European Southern Observatory, Karl-Schwarzschild-Str. 2, 85748 Garching-bei-München, Germany
e-mail: francesca.fragkoudi@eso.org

² Max-Planck-Institut für Astrophysik, Karl-Schwarzschild-Str. 1, 85748 Garching, Germany

³ Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Bologna, via Gobetti 93/2, I-40129 Bologna, Italy

⁴ Instituto de Investigación Multidisciplinar en Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad de La Serena, Raul Bitrán 1305, La Serena, Chile

⁵ Departamento de Astronomía, Universidad de La Serena, Av. Juan Cisternas 1200 Norte, La Serena, Chile

⁶ Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Victoria, Victoria, BC, V8P 5C2, Canada

Received xx xx; Accepted xx xx

2021

Fig. B.1. Bar properties as a function of time: *Top panel:* Bar strength for the five Auriga galaxies for which we have high cadence outputs as a function of lookback time. The horizontal dashed line indicates $A_2 = 0.2$ above which we consider the bar to have formed. *Bottom panel:* Bar pattern speed for these galaxies, once the bar is formed, as a function of lookback time.

This effect is seen in other simulations

less gas

more gas

pattern speed

softening

time

Open Questions

- Is the locking process numerical or physical in origin?
- There are several examples in the literature of no evolution (triaxial halo, spinning halo, cosmological, gas...). Is the locking process at play in other simulations?
- What gas fraction is really necessary? Is gas fraction the right metric, or surface density at bar tips?

Summary

We ran a simulation with Milky Way-like bar and realistic ISM

In this simulation, the bar has a constant pattern speed

We believe this is due to “bar locking” - a dramatic reduction in the halo torque

halo torques

reset halo

sanity check plot (not in paper)

((but probably should have been))

A self-regulating mechanism?

The bar cannot speed up arbitrarily

**It will encounter newly resonant
halo material**

An equilibrium mechanism?

**slowing down the
bar must cause it to
speed up faster**

**torque on
the bar by
the gas**

Separate disk
into "bar" and
"not bar"

total disk

A2,0

barred disk

unbarred disk

76% of A2,0

24% of A2,0

Mon. Not. R. Astron. Soc. **000**, 000–000 (0000) Printed 21 March 2019 (MN \LaTeX style file v2.2)

Using Harmonic Decomposition to Understand Barred Galaxy Evolution

Michael S. Petersen,^{1*} Martin D. Weinberg,¹ Neal Katz¹

¹University of Massachusetts at Amherst, 710 N. Pleasant St., Amherst, MA 01003

21 March 2019

ABSTRACT

We study the mechanisms and evolutionary phases of bar formation in n -body simulations of a stellar disc and dark matter halo system using harmonic basis function expansion analysis to characterize the dynamical mechanisms in bar evolution. We correlate orbit families with phases of bar evolution by using empirical orthogonal functions that act as a spatial filter and form the gravitational potential basis. In both models we find evidence for three phases in evolution with unique harmonic signatures. We recover known analytic results, such as bar slowdown owing to angular momentum transfer. We also find new dynamical mechanisms for bar evolution: a steady-state equilibrium configuration and harmonic interaction resulting in harmonic mode locking, both of which may be observable. Additionally, we find that ellipse fitting may severely overestimate measurements of bar length by a factor of two relative to the measurements based on orbits that comprise the true backbone supporting the bar feature. The bias will lead to overestimates of both bar mass and bar pattern speed, affecting inferences about the evolution of bars in the real universe, such as the fraction of bars with fast pattern speeds. We propose a direct observational technique to compute the radial extent of trapped orbits and determine a dynamical length for the bar.

Key words: galaxies: Galaxy: halo—galaxies: haloes—galaxies: kinematics and dynamics—galaxies: evolution—galaxies: structure

1 INTRODUCTION

The clear presence of responses to non-axisymmetric disturbances in galaxies—bars, spiral arms, warps, rings, and displacements, amongst other features—necessitate a higher-order harmonic description of stellar discs beyond an exponentially-decreasing monopole. Early studies characterized disc structure using Fourier amplitudes in rings of radius R , $A_m(R) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(R, \phi) e^{-im\phi} d\phi$ where m is the harmonic order and $f(R, \phi)$ is the weighting function corresponding to the luminosity (or ideally mass) as a function of azimuthal angle ϕ around the galaxy (Considere & Athanassoula 1988; Elmegreen et al. 1989). Barred galaxies, which make up more than half of the observed disc galaxies in the infrared (Sheth et al. 2008), are the most pronounced examples of galaxies with large

azimuthal structure and more accurately represents the gravitational field that causes the non-axisymmetric structures. One may then use the BFE measures to study the evolutionary mechanisms and scenarios for evolution. Connecting dynamical principles to galaxy evolutionary mechanisms to the BFE allows one to better study the evolutionary phases of barred galaxy evolution. In addition, a harmonic BFE analysis is an inexpensive way to parameterize both the evolution of large simulations and observational data.

The harmonic BFE decomposition technique has been used to both study and compare simulations, owing to its natural relationship with analytic perturbation theory (Weinberg & Katz 2007a,b). Some n -body simulations use a technique explicitly built on biorthogonal functions, where one solves the Poisson equation using separable azimuthal harmonics. Generally, these tech-

arXiv:1903.08203v1 [astro-ph.GA] 19 Mar 2019

L_z / l_z

**NOT A
SOLID
BODY**

pattern
speed

NOT A SOLID BODY

disk torquing

the average torque from $t=2$ to 4 Gyr on the bar by the disk in the Nbody case is 4.9 in code units ($1\text{E}10 \text{ Msun} (\text{km/s})^2$). In the SMUGGLE case it is -6.9.

Metastability

